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Befriending the Other as Nature's Recipe for Greater Stability and Prosperity

Job Kozhamthadam, *SI*
*Director, Indian Institute of
Science and Religion, Delhi*

Abstract: Perhaps the most baffling trait of the universe is its stability, despite its long history of almost 14 billion years, despite its almost limitless size and innumerable constituents, despite its state of continuous motion and complex interactions. This paper points out that mother nature achieves this extraordinary feat by using the strategy of befriending the other. It identifies some of the principal constituents and conditions involved in this strategy, and studies with concrete scientific examples how this strategy is applied at different levels of cosmic beings: human/rational (science-religion dialogue), biological (human body, carbon cycle, photosynthesis), and physical (solar system). The paper concludes by reflecting on what lesson we can learn from mother nature in this regard.

Keywords: interconnectedness, science-religion dialogue, stability of the universe, carbon-cycle, photosynthesis, stability of the solar system.

0. Introduction: Interconnectedness: A Fundamental Feature of the Cosmos

Interconnectedness is one of the most fascinating features of our universe. For a long time our sages and mystics

had come to notice this intuitively. Fortunately, in recent times contemporary science has been confirming this fact scientifically. Not only are the different constituents of the vast universe interlinked, within each individual member of the universe also we can see amazing interconnectedness. This observation has convinced thinkers like Immanuel Kant to look upon our universe as a unified whole. True, there are certain instances of disconnectedness and disharmony; there are also occasions of discord and dissonance. But it seems to me that in the vast ocean of order and harmony these should be taken as puddles of exceptions. It is important to recognize that this cosmic interconnectedness is not something peripheral and merely cosmetic – not something the universe can easily dispense with. Rather it is something fundamental and deep, substantial and essential for the universe since, as I shall point out, the universe depends on it in a significant way for its existence, preservation and smooth functioning. For instance, we know that the different planets and other heavenly bodies in the solar system are closely interlinked. Disturb any segment of it, the whole system goes out of step and eventually collapses. This interconnectedness is not confined to the physical world only, it is applicable also in the biological as well as rational/human world. Again, interconnectedness is found not merely between beings of the same type. It is found also among items which appear to be different and unrelated – at a deeper level these dissimilar beings are found to be deeply and intimately related. Often this discovery of the deeper linkage and unity between apparently dissimilar candidates can serve as a source of growth and enrichment since this process involves tapping the resources from different sources. For instance, at first glance it may look that science and religion have hardly anything in common, but, as will be discussed later, deeper interaction and reflection can show that they have much in common, and pooling these resources can trigger greater growth and enrichment. It is in this kind of context

that ‘befriending the other’ becomes a successful strategy for mutual growth and enrichment. This paper is a detailed study of some of the salient features and benefits of ‘befriending the other’ at the different levels of existence – rational/human, biological and physical. At all these levels it will be seen that befriending the other is an effective way for greater growth and development. It will also study some of the implications of this strategy and practice.

1. Befriending the Other – Exploring the Concept

It may be useful to deal with this issue from various perspectives.

a. Some Features of Befriending the Other, Particularly at the Human Level

Befriending the other is a process, a complex process, involving many aspects. It is important that we unpack this rich concept in the beginning itself. First of all, as mentioned already, we need to keep in mind that this process is not limited to the rational, human level only. It is universal, embracing the different levels of existence: the rational level in humans, the biological level in living beings and the physical level in the physical nature. However, the process of befriending the other is most commonly and frequently studied and practiced at the level of humans. Hence now we will enter into a short discussion of what it means to befriend the other at the human level.

We can befriend the other at the human level in many different ways. Jean-Paul Sartre, for instance, has a very negative and pessimistic view of the other when he says: “hell is other people.” Jesus Christ, on the other hand, asks us to consider the other as our brother and sister. In fact, he goes much further to identify the other with himself: “When you did it to the least of my brothers and sisters, you did it to me.”

For Jesus and his genuine followers the principle and practice of befriending the other is very positive; it takes the other as a friend, not as an alien.

Again, the spirit of befriending the other looks upon the other as a person, who is an end in himself/herself. It can never look upon the other as an object to be used. The other is a person with rights and privileges, duties and obligations, freedom and limitations, likes and dislikes. Befriending the other means recognizing all these different dimensions and taking them into serious consideration while dealing with him/her.

The other becomes a close collaborator in the context of befriending the other. It means that the other is considered an equal partner having something valuable to contribute. It means also having confidence in the sincerity and seriousness, competence and capability of the other. It involves listening to the other with care and attention.

The attitude that should animate the spirit of befriending the other is one of openness and positiveness. It involves accepting the limitedness of one's own resources, and being ready to welcome the almost unlimited resources available in others outside. This positive attitude does not mean uncritically acquiescing to the other, rather it means a willingness to agree joyfully and a readiness to disagree gracefully.

The benefits one can reap from the positive approach of befriending the other are many. It leads to greater efficiency by dividing the labour and multiplying the benefits. It can be a source of joy and consolation since it often involves dividing the pain of the struggle and multiplying the joy of the reward. It results in the redoubling of the resources since the resources of the other also become available for the common good.

b. Some Important Conditions of the Process of Befriending the Other

In general to render the process of befriending the other an enriching experience a number of conditions or requirements can be of help, some of which are given below.

1. The process of befriending involves a complex issue having many essential components or partners.
2. The components or partners often differ significantly from each other.
3. The outcome cannot be achieved by any one of the components or partners alone.
4. Each component or partner brings in something essential for the outcome, which the others cannot.
5. The outcome achieved benefits the whole system.

As has been mentioned already, the process of befriending the other is universal, cutting across all forms and levels of being. Furthermore, this can take place at different levels and in different forms. It can take the form of interaction among the different partners; it can take the form of dialogue between the different parties, etc. In all these cases, it is expected that the attitude taken and the spirit animating is one of mutual respect, mutual understanding, genuine openness and creative concern for the general good. Also in this context special effort is made to focus on what is common to all, what unites all with a common goal.

To substantiate our claim that the process of befriending is universally applicable, and exercised at all levels, we will take up different cases from the three realms of existence – the human/rational, the biological and the physical.

2. Befriending the Other at Different Levels

We may talk of befriending at various levels.

A. The Human/Rational World – Science-Religion Dialogue (SRD)

i. Science and Religion and Their Need

Science and religion arguably are two most powerful influences in our world today, having vast resources and affecting our lives most profoundly. In some significant ways they shape our worldviews, set our goals, form our value system and control our ambitions and aspirations. Since they are very different from each other, there may not be any natural tendency to pool their resources together. At the same time, it is well known that they both have much to offer to humans, and the human race will be far better off if their vast resources can be brought together for the betterment of humans and society. This is what science-religion dialogue attempts to achieve.

ii. Science-Religion Dialogue – Its Nature and Significance

Although science-religion dialogue is as old as science itself, it is quite recent as a systematic, interdisciplinary field, particularly in the academic circles. Inherently general and interdisciplinary, it is open to many forms and interpretations. I look upon it as an attempt to bring together the latest findings of modern science and the deepest insights of religions in order to build up a better humanity in the multireligious, multicultural and multiracial context of our globalizing world. Obviously, it is open to all religions and all branches of modern science, including social sciences. It is based on the belief that both science and religion are the most powerful influences in our society today, wielding tremendous power in shaping our attitudes, meaning-system, value-system, etc. A well-informed approach to issues with mutual respect for the

perspectives of each other, openness to new possibilities, and readiness to change are the trademark of this field. Although the initial stages of science-religion interfacing were marked by unsureness about its feasibility, uncertainty about its capability and doubts about its success,¹ today this field has undergone a quantum leap, moving to the central stage of academic research and study, engaging many outstanding scientists, philosophers, theologians and other thinkers all over the world, thanks, to a great extent, to the substantial support and encouragement, especially monetary, it has been receiving from generous patrons like the John Templeton Foundation. It seems that almost every month a new book is out on the subject; frequent conferences, seminars and symposia are held in various parts of the world as a matter of routine. India has been making its share of contribution, particularly at the Indian Institute of Science and Religion (IISR), Delhi, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth (JDV) Centre for Science and Religion (JCSR), Pune, Institute of Science and Religion, Aluva, Kerala, Science and Religion Samgam, Goa, etc. For instance, on the average once every month IISR has been conducting programs in this field in some college or academic institution in India, and the response has always been very positive and encouraging.

iii. Different Models of Science-Religion Interaction

Although there is near unanimity concerning the importance of science and religion as the two most powerful influences in our world today, with regard to the relationship between the two no such unanimity is forthcoming. The pioneering work of Ian Barbour identifies 4 different models: Conflict, Independence, Dialogue and Integration. John Haught, on the other hand, suggests Conflict, Contrast, Contact, and Confirmation. Ted Peters goes on to present eight different models to account for the complex relationship between science and religion. My own study and reflection on the

matter has identified mainly 3 different models: Conflict, Compartmenting and Complementarity. It seems to me that the many models suggested by various scholars can, with appropriate adaptation, be shown to be different variants of these three basic models. When we come to certain specific cases, this relationship can be highly complex, defying any attempt to reduce it to a single model. For instance, my own study of the relationship between Catholicism and modern science over the centuries shows that the relationship went through three different stages: Encouragement, Estrangement and Engagement.² When modern science was in its infancy, the Catholic Church encouraged it enthusiastically. However, later on a period of estrangement ensued, the classic instances being the unfortunate and avoidable Galileo episode and the Darwinian controversy. Later on this period of estrangement gave way to the period of engagement, the state the dialogue between the Catholic Church and science is in today.

a. The Conflict View

The fundamental idea of the conflict view is that science and religion are not only radically different, but also are antagonists constantly at war with each other, with science mostly at the winner's seat. Over the years science has been winning, and it is only a matter of time before it attains total victory, while religion gets vanquished.

“The boom of science is the doom of religion” is the standard slogan of this view. In the past this model was considered almost the standard view on the relationship between science and religion. Even today this remains the most common popular perception on the matter, thanks mainly to the popular cliché-driven media which often uncritically presents this view. This view has been propounded by Logical Positivism and other atheistic systems of thought.

John William Draper (1811–1882) in his book of 1874, *The History of the Conflict between Religion and Science*, and Andrew D. White (1832-1918) in his book of 1896, *A History of the Warfare of Science with Theology in Christendom*, contributed considerably towards popularizing this view. However, in recent times this view has come under severe criticism, in light of serious study and research in the history of science by eminent scholars.³ It is true that in the context of religious fundamentalism and scientific materialism this view may get some support, but these cannot be considered legitimate representatives of religion and science. Today very few scholars subscribe to this view. My own study and reflection on the matter reveals to me that this conflict view is more the creation of certain historians of science with vested interest than of historical data.⁴

b. Compartmenting View

The basic idea of this model is that science and religion are two valid, legitimate systems, but they remain independent and do not interact. The claims they have and the statements they make are legitimate and worthy of respect and acceptance in their own respective domains, having no significant impact on others. Classical statements like “When Faraday opens the door of his oratory, he closes the door of his laboratory,” bring home the spirit and substance of this position. In the past many scientists used to subscribe to this view, particularly since it avoided most forms of controversy and consequent tension. In recent times Stephen J Gould in his *Rocks of Ages: Science and Religion in the Fullness of Life* has brought back this view under the title NOMA (Non-Overlapping Magisteria).⁵

c. Complementarity View

The complementarity view, which I consider the best to describe the complex relationship between science and religion, respects and accepts both science and religion as very important

and legitimate areas of importance in our world, particularly in the life of humans. Each has very valuable and even necessary contribution to make. Each is legitimate, but differs substantially from the other. The two are complementary in the sense that one brings in something important and necessary which the other does not and cannot. It is also found that for the fullness of human life both are needed since human life will be incomplete and impoverished if either one is missing. It may be noted that the complementarity relationship takes place not so much at the level of a particular theory or law in science, or a particular belief or dogma in religion as at the level of human life – they complement each other at the level of the lived life and deep experience of humans. For human life to be complete and fruitful the contribution from both is needed. Some representative statements illustrating this relationship are: “Science without religion is lame, religion without science is blind.” (Einstein). “Science can purify religion from error and superstition; religion can purify science from idolatry and false absolutes.” (Pope John Paul II). “Science does not need religion (mysticism); religion does not need science; but man needs both.” (Fritjof Capra). It seems to me that today many scholars, particularly scientists, are becoming more and more inclined to embrace this complementarity view.

B. Befriending the Other at the Biological Level

i. Befriending of the Different Components (interconnectedness) of the Human Body

The human body is a miracle of coordination and collaboration of the constituent parts. It has been estimated that an average human body has 100 trillion cells. We know that in each cell there is a DNA molecule with about 3.1 billion base units, each of which is made of many atoms. From atomic theory it is known that each atom comprises many elementary particles like proton, neutron, electron, etc. Now the remarkable point is that all these are constantly moving and carrying

out important functions. The movements and activities of such an incredible number of particles will have to be carefully coordinated and harmoniously blended to make the human body function normally. These innumerable components will have to adjust, accommodate and collaborate. This is a beautiful illustrative instance of befriending the other taking place all the time in the biological world, which ensures the stability and healthy functioning of the biological world.

ii. The Carbon Cycle – Photosynthesis-Respiration Cycle

a. Different Natural Cycles

Our universe is blessed with a series of natural cycles – Carbon Cycle, Nitrogen Cycle, Phosphorus Cycle, Water Cycle, etc. A natural cycle is a phenomenon involving the use and reuse of a limited quantity of resources for an indefinite length of time. It involves several stages which are arranged in such a way that the end of the first stage becomes the beginning of the second, etc. Also what is remarkable about this process is that the waste product of one stage becomes the principal raw material for the next stage. This phenomenon is indeed an ingenious master-stroke of our mother nature wherein the minimum amount of resources is used to get the maximum output to carry out very vital functions. The natural cycle is a supreme display of nature's uncanny wisdom, unmatched economy and amazing efficiency.

b. The Carbon Cycle

Carbon cycle is a process in which carbon moves from one stage to another in a cyclic way performing important functions. Carbon is essential for life and living beings. But there is only a limited supply of it in nature. The carbon cycle process enables nature to carry out all these functions with this limited supply. The carbon cycle process can be considered a very interesting illustrative case of befriending the other in ac-

tion in nature because it involves the participation of different levels of beings – physical world, plant kingdom, animal kingdom and even humans. All these different partners contribute and collaborate, mutually ensuring that the life functions are carried out efficiently and smoothly for the common wellbeing. To illustrate the point, let us consider photosynthesis, a process in which plants prepare sugars or carbohydrates by using carbon dioxide from the atmosphere as well as water in the presence of sunlight. In this process oxygen is also produced. Next comes respiration in which oxygen is taken in by animals and humans and carbon dioxide is produced which is discharged into the atmosphere to start the cycle all over again. Thus we see in this process the different items collaborate and mutually adjust to produce results for the common good. Here one item in nature befriends another apparently unrelated item to produce results that are beneficial for all the parties concerned.

C. Befriending the Other at the Physical Level

i. In the Astronomical World

Although contemporary science offers many pieces of evidence for the finiteness of the universe, there is no consensus with regard to the number of galaxies or the total number of stars in the universe. Some reliable estimates say that there are 100 billion galaxies, and in each one of them there are about 100 billion stars, thus putting the total number of stars at 10^{22} . Each star has its own star system, just like our solar system, with planets, satellites, comets, asteroids, etc. The total number of heavenly bodies is simply mind-boggling. Even more amazing is the fact that none of them is stationary; all are moving constantly in complex motions. And yet they do not seem to be getting in the way of each other or disturbing the stability and normal functioning of the universe! They must be moving and interacting with each other in a highly coordi-

nated and collaborative way to allow the smooth functioning of this vast universe. This is another magnificent display of befriending the other in nature, in the physical universe.

ii. The Stability of the Solar System

According to some calculations, it is about 5 billion years since the solar system was born, and it may be another 5 billion years before the sun dies. The solar system is expected to remain stable for all practical purposes for this long span of time, although recent studies show some difficulties in the long run in this regard. The stability of the solar system was a major puzzle for Newton. He studied this problem at considerable length in 1687 and could not find any natural, scientific explanation for this stability. Since he was a firm believer in the rationality of nature, according to which all natural phenomena should have a genuine cause, he invoked the periodic divine intervention to explain this stability. According to him, God periodically intervened to ensure that the solar system was maintained in its original condition. However, Laplace, building on the works of Euler and Lagrange, showed the dispensability of any such outside divine intervention. Laplace studied the motion of Jupiter and Saturn and found certain anomalies in their motion: Jupiter's orbit appeared to be shrinking, while that of Saturn was expanding. He showed that this was due to "the gravitational attraction of each planet upon the other." He found that any two planets and the sun must be in mutual equilibrium. Generalizing the results of his investigation, Laplace pointed out that the total eccentricity of the planetary orbits of the solar system had to remain constant. This meant that the eccentricities of planets would have to be balanced. If the eccentricity of any one planet increased, then that of the other planets should decrease such that a balance would be maintained. It was also found that the same balancing arrangement would hold in the case of the inclination of a planet's orbit to the plane of the ecliptic. In short, mutual co-

operation and mutual adjustment was the secret of the stability of the solar system. According to Gerald James Whitrow, the work of Laplace was “the most important advance in physical astronomy since Newton.”⁶

It may be noted that in light of more recent studies on the solar system, the findings of Laplace are found to be only approximate, and can ensure only limited stability for a limited time. Recent studies lead scientists to conclude that the solar system is chaotic, although it happens to be somewhat stable. My point, as far as this discussion is concerned, is that this remarkable stability, albeit limited, of the solar system has come about because it has been exercising the strategy of befriending the other. This stability is the end result of mutual collaboration and adjustment by the different partners for a common good.

A similar process is responsible for the stability of the earth’s orbit around the sun. Primarily two forces are involved here: The gravitational force between the sun and the earth because of which the earth is pulled in and the centrifugal force due to the curved motion of the earth because of which the earth holds out. The stability is achieved by the mutual adjustment of the two forces: If the earth is too far out, gravity pulls it back; if it is too close, the centrifugal force pushes it back out. Similar is the case with other bodies going around the sun. The way our nature operates is indeed amazing, and in these situations the process of befriending the other is going on.

3. Some Significant Implications

a. Stability and Prosperity Achieved through Befriending the Other

The brief study above shows that the strategy of befriending the other carries with it many welcome rewards. The cases we discussed show that nature has used it to achieve much-

needed and hard-to-get stability and smooth functioning. It can be a reliable path to growth and prosperity. Nature teaches us in this context that the universe and beings in it can draw strength and stability through collaboration and partnership, while they collapse and destroy themselves if they remain in isolation.

b. Further Evidence for the Deeper Unity of the Universe

The process of befriending the other is not limited to a small part of the universe, rather it is found at all levels of being: human/rational, biological and physical. It seems to be a fundamental feature of the universe, thereby offering further evidence for the deeper unity of the universe.

c. Everyone Counts, Everyone Has a Definite Role to Play

In this strategy of befriending everyone counts. For it to be successful everyone has to contribute, everyone has to play a definite role. Hence none can be bypassed or ignored. Everyone needs to be taken seriously and respectfully.

d. Need to Develop Skills in Interpersonal Interaction

One of the lessons we can take home from this study and reflection is that to befriend the other successfully the right way of interacting is necessary. At the human level this calls for developing skills in interpersonal interaction.

4. Conclusion: Befriending the Other in a Globalizing World

We live in a world that is globalizing continuously. This naturally calls for interacting with people of different cultural, racial, religious, educational and personal background. Only by learning to befriend them creatively and constructively can one get ahead in this globalizing world. As the world

gets more and more globalized, the need for befriending the other becomes more and more necessary.

As Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth is celebrating the Diamond Jubilee of its new home in Pune, it can proudly recall its own contribution to the process of befriending the other. For the last 122 years in general and for the last 60 years in particular JDV has been serving as a catalyst in the process of befriending the other – bringing peoples together, religions together, cultures together, disciplines together, binding them creatively and harmoniously to be ambassadors of love, joy, peace and harmony. May it continue this noble mission in the years to come! May it continue to inspire and guide men and women from all corners of India and abroad in this great art of befriending the other!

Notes

1. I remember in 1980 when I told a few eminent professors of the universities in New York that I was planning to do my doctoral dissertation in the area of science-religion dialogue, they gave me a wide look of surprise and discouragement. In their verbal communication they told me that the subject was too vague and unsystematic, and so no good work could come out of it. But the non-verbal communication was loud and clear: This Indian must be living out of this world, with no knowledge of what he is talking about!
2. For a detailed discussion of this point see Job Kozhamthadam, “The Changing Face of Science-Christianity Dialogue: Encouragement, Estrangement and Engagement,” in Job Kozhamthadam, ed., *Science, Technology and Values: Science-Religion Dialogue in a Multi-Religious World* (Pune: ASSR Publications, 2003), pp.3-34.
3. See Stephen J Gould, *Rocks of Ages: Science and Religion in the Fullness of Life* (New York: Ballantine Publishing Group, 1999).
4. For instance, see Job Kozhamthadam, “The Galileo Episode Revisited,” *Vidyajyoti* 58 (1994), 337–358.

5. See note 2.

6. See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pierre-Simon_Laplace accessed on 2/11/2015.

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